

CONTRIBUTION FROM SHEAR IN THE ELASTIC CURVE OF GLUED LAMINATED TIMBER BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental study of contribution of shearing forces in the elastic curve of glued laminated timber beams. The elastic curve was plotted from displacements measured at 14 points through the beam span by magnetic transducers. Contribution from shear was determined by using the general equation for the elastic curve, disregarding only cross-sectional warping influence. Results indicated a perfect match between experimental values and theoretical model and an small contribution from shear was detected in elastic curve for beams of span/height ratio (L/d) over 21.

Keywords: glulam, shearing forces and wooden structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminated glued timber (glulam), due to the fact of being a composite material formed of thin-multilayered-glued sheets is not easy to model mathematically and studies should be conducted experimentally.

In this work the influence of shearing effort in elastic curve will be studied for glulam beams in order to obtain its magnitude and, by using this data, determine the longitudinal modulus of elasticity for the glulam beam through a simple flexural experiment.

Elastic curve will be determined experimentally through displacement measurements at 14 points. A comparative study between elastic curve obtained experimentally and the theoretical one will be presented, considering bending as well as shearing effort.

2. ELASTIC CURVE EQUATION

Elastic curve equation may be expressed in 3 parts: (1) flexural deformation due to bending moment (M); (2) angular deflection due to shear (V) and (3) angular deflection due to cross sectional warping. This last one is very small for no-slender full section beams and will not be

considered in this work. So, the elastic curve equation may be written as an algebraic sum of part (1) and (2) mentioned above, by:

$$v = v_b + v_s \tag{1}$$

where v_b is the parcel due to flexural deformation and v_s is due to shearing effort.

2.1. Bending moment contribution (v_b)

Consider the glulam beam schematized in Figure 1 subjected to a 1 kN concentrated load.

Figure 1. Elastic curve for beam subjected to 1 concentrated load

The elastic curve equation, taking into account bending moment contribution only and considering small deformations, is given by:

$$\frac{d^2 v_b}{dx^2} = -\frac{M}{EI} \quad \text{or} \quad EI v_b'' = -M \tag{2}$$

Due to discontinuity of the slope of the bending moment, Equation 2 should be written in two parts:

$$EI v_b'' = -\frac{Nx}{2} \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \tag{3}$$

$$EI v_b'' = -\frac{Nx}{2} + N(x - \frac{L}{2}) \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \tag{4}$$

Integrating Equation 3 and 4 twice, we obtain:

$$EI v_b = -\frac{Nx^3}{12} + C_1 x + C_3 \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \tag{5}$$

$$EI v_b = -\frac{Nx^3}{12} + N \frac{(x - \frac{L}{2})^3}{6} + C_2 x + C_4 \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \tag{6}$$

where C_1 , C_2 , C_3 and C_4 are constants which can be obtained from boundary conditions as following:

- For $x = L/2$ elastic curve tangent for equation 3 is equal to Equation 4. This implies $C_1 = C_2$.
- For $x = L/2$ displacements are equal for Equation 5 and Equation 6. This implies $C_3 = C_4$.
- For $x = 0$ and $x = L/2$ displacements are equal to zero. Finally, we have $C_1 = C_2 = 3NL^2/48$ and $C_3 = C_4 = 0$ and the elastic curve is:

$$v_b = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} \left[3\frac{x}{L} - 4\left(\frac{x}{L}\right)^3 \right] \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad (07)$$

$$v_b = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} \left[3\frac{x}{L} - 4\left(\frac{x}{L}\right)^3 + 8\left(\frac{x}{L} - \frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \right] \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \quad (08)$$

$$f_{b,max} = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} \quad x = L/2 \quad (09)$$

Similarly, for a beam subjected to two-symmetrically concentrated loads ($N/2$) as in Figure 2, we obtain:

$$v_b = \frac{Na^3}{12EI} \left[3\left(1 + \frac{b}{a}\right)\frac{x}{a} - \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^3 \right] \quad a \leq x \leq a \quad (10)$$

$$v_b = \frac{Na^3}{12EI} \left[3\left(1 + \frac{b}{a}\right)\frac{x}{a} - \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{x}{a} - 1\right)^3 \right] \quad a \leq x \leq a + b \quad (11)$$

$$v_b = \frac{Na^3}{12EI} \left[3\left(1 + \frac{b}{a}\right)\frac{x}{a} - \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{x}{a} - 1\right)^3 + \left(\frac{x}{a} - \frac{b}{a} - 1\right)^3 \right] \quad a + b \leq x \leq L \quad (12)$$

$$f_{b,max} = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} \left[3\frac{a}{L} - 4\left(\frac{a}{L}\right)^3 \right] \quad x = L/2 \quad (13)$$

Figure 2 . Elastic curve for a beam subjected to 2 concentrated loads.

2.2. Shearing force contribution (vs)

Shearing stresses, for rectangular cross sectional beams, produce a deformation of an element dx as showed in Figure 3. Since shearing stresses vary along the height of the beam, the cross section turns into curved surfaces. Original axis of the beam, in Figure 3, is represented by line mn , assumed horizontal, and mp shows its position after angular deflection.

Figure 3. Angular deflection [1].

Admitting that element sides are kept in vertical position at m and n, upper and lower edges will be parallel to mp with an angle αc with horizontal (αc is the angular deflection of the neutral axis). The element deformation may be easily visualized by dividing it into parts, each one under pure shearing force (Figure 3-b). The deflection of Part 1 is αc . In the lowest part, 4, deflection must be zero and angles between its sides will be of 90 .

Elastic curve tangent for the beam due to shearing only is approximately equal to angular deflection of the neutral axis, Figure 3-a, and is given by:

$$\frac{dv_s}{dx} = \gamma_c = \frac{\alpha_c V}{GA} \quad (14)$$

where V/A is the average shearing stress; αc is a coefficient (shearing coefficient or shape coefficient) defined as the relation between shearing stress at neutral axis and average shearing stress, and G is the transverse modulus of elasticity.

According to [1], for a rectangular cross-section, the value of αc is $3/2$. By integration of three-dimensional equations of elasticity, an equivalent value of 1.18 was determined [2].

For a single beam with one mid span concentrated load (Figure 1) the equation of elastic curve due to shearing effort is:

$$\frac{d^2 v_s}{dx^2} = 0 \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{d^2 v_s}{dx^2} = 0 \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \quad (16)$$

By integration of Equations 15 and 16 we have:

$$\frac{dv_s}{dx} = C_1 \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{dv_s}{dx} = C_2 \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \quad (18)$$

It shows that elastic curve inclination through the beam span due to shear is constant. This inclination, in accordance with Equation 14 is $\alpha c V/GA$. By continuity condition C_1 is equal to C_2 . Integrating again, we have:

$$v_s = C_1 x + C_3 \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad (19)$$

$$v_s = C_1 x + C_4 \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \quad (20)$$

Imposing the following conditions: $v_s = 0$ for $x = 0$, $v_s = 0$ for $x = L$ and equal displacements at mid span, and knowing that $v = N/2$ for $x < L/2$; $v = -N/2$ for $x > L/2$, the constant values will be $C_1 = C_2 = \alpha c V / 2GA$; $C_3 = 0$; $C_4 = \alpha c V / GSL$. Finally, the elastic curve equation due to shearing is:

$$v_s = \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} x \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad (21)$$

$$v_s = \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} (L - x) \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \quad (22)$$

$$v_{s,max} = \frac{\alpha_c N}{4GA} L \quad x = L/2 \quad (23)$$

Similarly for a double loaded beam, as in Figure 2, we have:

$$v_s = \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} x \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad (24)$$

$$v_s = \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} a \quad a \leq x \leq (a + b) \quad (25)$$

$$v_s = \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} (L - x) \quad a + b \leq x \leq L \quad (26)$$

$$v_{s,max} = \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} a \quad a \leq x \leq a + b \quad (27)$$

Finally, the elastic curve equation considering bending and shear ($v = v_b + v_s$), with a one-concentrated load N at mid span is given by:

$$v = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} \left[3\frac{x}{L} - 4\left(\frac{x}{L}\right)^3 \right] + \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} x \quad 0 \leq x \leq L/2 \quad (28)$$

$$v = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} \left[3\frac{x}{L} - 4\left(\frac{x}{L}\right)^3 + 8\left(\frac{x}{L} - \frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \right] + \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} (L - x) \quad L/2 \leq x \leq L \quad (29)$$

$$v_{max} = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} + \frac{\alpha_c N}{4GA} L \quad x = L/2 \quad (30)$$

For a single-beam with two symmetric loads $N/2$, the elastic curve equation is given by:

$$v = \frac{Na^3}{12EI} \left[3\left(1 + \frac{b}{a}\right)\frac{x}{a} - \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^3 \right] + \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} x \quad 0 \leq x \leq a \quad (31)$$

$$v = \frac{Na^3}{12EI} \left[3\left(1 + \frac{b}{a}\right)\frac{x}{a} - \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{x}{a} - 1\right)^3 \right] + \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} a \quad a \leq x \leq (a + b) \quad (32)$$

$$v = \frac{Na^3}{12EI} \left[3\left(1 + \frac{b}{a}\right)\frac{x}{a} - \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{x}{a} - 1\right)^3 + \left(\frac{x}{a} - \frac{b}{a} - 1\right)^3 \right] + \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} (L - x) \quad (a + b) \leq x \leq L \quad (33)$$

$$v_{max} = \frac{NL^3}{48EI} \left[3\left(\frac{a}{L}\right) - 4\left(\frac{a}{L}\right)^3 \right] + \frac{\alpha_c N}{2GA} a \quad a \leq x \leq (a + b) \quad (34)$$

3. EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF ELASTIC CURVE

A series of experiments was conducted [3] in order to determine the experimental elastic curve of a beam with span of 11,70m and cross-section with 39.05cm x 870cm composed of 11 sheets with 3.55cm of thickness.

For the experiment 14 magnetic transducers (LVDT's) were placed through the beam span: 7 in the lower left-side and another 7 in the upper right-side as showed in Figure 4-b. This configuration was chosen in order to avoid the possibility of incorrect lecture due to a possible torsion of the beam, although bracing was supplied at 5 points along its span, as showed in Figure 4-b and 4-d. A general view of the transducers position and bracing is showed in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Scheme of the experiment and instrumentation

Twelve tests were conducted: 6 with a mid span concentrated load (2 for $L/d = 21$, 2 for $L/d = 18$ and 2 for $L/d = 14$) and 6 others were conducted for a beam with symmetrically concentrated loads with 1,80m between each other (2 for $L/d = 21$, 2 for $L/d = 18$ and 2 for $L/d = 14$). Experiments were performed for the beam in both direct and inverted positions.

4. DISCUSSION AND COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL RESULTS

Measurements taken by magnetic transducers (LVDT's) for 3 levels of loads are presented in Table 1. An example of elastic curve graphic is showed in Figure 5. It suggests a parabolic curve as an approximation for the elastic curve.

Figure 5. Elastic curve obtained experimentally

For comparison of the elastic curve obtained experimentally and the theoretical one, Equations 7 to 13 were taken to determine the contribution due to bending moment; Equations 21 to 27 to determine shearing force contribution and finally, Equations 28 to 34 to take into account the bending moment plus shearing force contribution. This comparison was carried out considering firstly, the average of longitudinal modulus of elasticity (E_s) of 64 points of the glulam beam for which E_s and G_s were determined and, finally, by using horizontally and vertically homogenized E . Equations 35 to 37, used for this homogenization, are presented below:

$$t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m E_i h_i [\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} h_j + (\frac{h_i}{2})]}{\sum_{i=1}^m E_i h_i} \quad GA = G_1 db \quad (35)$$

$$EI = b \sum_{i=1}^m [E_i \frac{h_i^3}{12} + E_i h_i \{ [t - (\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} h_j + \frac{h_i}{2})]^2 \}] \quad (36)$$

$$d_t = \sqrt{12 \sum_{i=1}^m \{ \frac{h_i^3}{12} (\frac{G_i}{G_1}) + h_i (\frac{G_i}{G_1}) [t - (\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} h_j + \frac{h_i}{2})]^2 \}} \quad (37)$$

where t = position of the neutral axis; EI = stiffness of the horizontally homogenized beam; GA = transverse stiffness of vertically homogenized beam and d_t = height of vertically homogenized beam.

The average value of modulus of elasticity obtained for all the laminae was practically equal to the homogenized modulus for the glulam beam (difference of 1.18%). Figure 6 shows two diagrams of elastic curves. The first one was obtained by using the average value of modulus of elasticity for all laminae and the second by using the homogenized modulus. There is no considerable difference between them. Experimental elastic curve for a beam subjected to one and two concentrated loads are showed in Figure 7 and 8, respectively, represented by the symbol "o" and data obtained theoretically are symbolized by a dashed line (----) for bending moment contribution, by dash-pointed line (-.-.-) for shearing effort contribution and by a pointed line (.....) for the sum of both contributions. The double-dash pointed line (=.=.=) is a simple linear regression of experimental results (460 points per each experiment).

Figure 6. Comparison of elastic curves for average modulus of elasticity (a) and homogenized (b)

Figure 7. Elastic curve obtained experimentally and theoretically for $L/d = 21$

Figure 8. Elastic curve obtained experimentally and theoretically

5. CONCLUSION

Observing and comparing the figures we realize that as the L/d ratio decreases the influence of shearing effort increases. However this increment does not go over 6%. Analyzing the difference between values of modulus determined through a regression and values of elastic curve due to bending moment contribution, it indicates that this difference decreases when L/d ratio increases, stabilizing for values of L/d over 21. In conclusion, the elastic curve, the modulus of elasticity and the deflection at mid span can be determined by a flexural experiment with $L/d > 21$.

References

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AN INVERSE PROBLEM IN DESIGNING LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

An integrated approach is introduced for the solution of the inverse problem: which are the lamina orientation, laminate constitution, core quality and thickness combination ensuring specified objective(s) to be reached?

The solution is obtained by integrating around an associative data base - sensitivity analysis and mathematically stringent optimization methods (MMA-Method of Moving Asymptotes) with finite element analysis, interactive graphic pre- and post-processing and parametric modelling - as implemented in OASIS-ALADDIN.

This approach has been applied to the design of a composite blade with adaptive characteristics -i.e a blade with decreasing pitch for increasing loads.

Keywords: Inverse Problem, Optimization, Sensitivity Analysis, Composites, Adaptive Structures

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are today increasingly used for weight and/or performance sensitive structures. The heterogeneous nature of laminated fiber-reinforced composites allows engineers to customize the material and to design the structure as to reach an optimal solution, on a technical and economical basis. Given the number of parameters to take into account, the best possible design can only be achieved through a long iterative procedure of analysis and modification.

In this paper we introduce an integrated approach for the solution of the inverse problem: which are the lamina orientation, laminate constitution, core quality and thickness combination ensuring specified objective(s) to be reached?

The solution is obtained by integrating around an associative data base - sensitivity analysis and mathematically stringent optimization methods (MMA-Method of Moving Asymptotes) with finite element analysis, interactive graphic pre- and post-processing and parametric modelling - as implemented in OASIS-ALADDIN.

Thus the optimization of local and global geometry; laminate and lamina thicknesses; material orientation (e.g. fiber angles); and material quality (e.g. sandwich foam core densities) can be performed. The shape optimization concept is based on parametric B-rep solid modelling formulations and is fully 3-D. Objective and constraint functions may be structural weight, mass moment of inertia, stiffness, natural frequency, stresses and material cost, as well as arbitrary linear combinations of these. Objective and constraint functions may also be defined as explicit linear functions of the design variables. The objective may be given as minimizing or maximizing a single function or a combination of several functions, or as minimizing the maximum of a set of functions.